

Секція 2. ЕКОНОМІКА ПІДПРИЄМСТВ ХАРЧУВАННЯ ТА ТОРГІВЛІ

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FEATURES OF ACTIVITIES OF TRADE ENTERPRISES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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The article dwells upon the analysis of modern trends in the development of trade enterprises in Ukraine. It presents the results of key indicators of retail distributors in dynamics and studies the directions of development of local retail networks.

Keywords: trade enterprise, retail trade, commodity circulation, retail distribution network, external environment.

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ ТОРГІВЛІ В СУЧАСНИХ УМОВАХ

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Проаналізовано сучасні тенденції розвитку підприємств торгівлі в Україні. Подано результати ключових показників діяльності підприємств роздрібної торгівлі в динаміці й досліджено напрями розвитку локальних торгових мереж.

У процесі реформування економіки України відбуваються суспільно-економічні зміни, що стосуються широкого спектра видів діяльності та галузей, зокрема сфери роздрібної торгівлі, для якої визначальною є конкурентна поведінка окремих підприємств. Результатом економічної реформи торгівлі в сучасному конкурентному середовищі є багатокладність форм власності й можливість розвитку різних типів торговельних підприємств. Торгівля відіграє важливу роль у формуванні конкурентного середовища, реалізації соціальної політики та ринкової орієнтації національної економіки, адже являє собою канал просування продукції до споживача, вид економічної діяльності, об'єктом якої є товарообмін та обслуговування покуців із продажу товарів, їх транспортування, зберігання та підготовки до продажу.

Запорукою виживання багатьох компаній у період посиленої турбулентності зовнішнього середовища стає оптимізація власного потенціалу. Однак у таких умовах, коли значно загострюється конкуренція, підприємство може втратити власні ринкові переваги. Така модель

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управління, що враховує фактор нестійкості, являє собою нову систему і набір стратегічних принципів, розроблених для сприяння бізнесу під час успішного переходу до «нової реальності» й отримання прибутку в довгостроковій перспективі, незалежно від економічних умов.

У результаті аналітичного дослідження зовнішнього середовища функціонування підприємств торгівлі зроблено висновок, що в цілому торговельна галузь України має позитивну динаміку розвитку. Збільшення обсягів роздрібно-го товарообігу дає додатковий поштовх для розвитку економіки країни в цілому. Однак перманентна політична нестабільність України, напружена військово-політична ситуація, падіння реальних доходів українців та відповідно тотальне зниження платоспроможності населення, погіршення основних макроекономічних показників економіки України, знецінення гривні призводять до дестабілізації роботи всіх соціально-економічних систем, що відбивається й на динаміці стану та розвитку підприємств роздрібно-го торгівлі України.

На фоні загострення політичної ситуації в Україні змінюється економічна ситуація – коливання курсу долара негативно впливає на ціни товарів, адже підприємці, щоб перестрахуватись, піднімають ціни в національній валюті, що негативно позначається на попиті, оскільки покупці змінюють закупівельні звички, переходячи на більш дешеві альтернативи повсякденних продуктів, та відповідно відбивається на роздрібно-му товарообігу.

За підсумками аналітичних досліджень статистики роздрібно-го торгівлі відзначено, що серед основних тенденцій розвитку роздрібно-го торгівлі в Україні можна виділити: зростання показника роздрібно-го товарообігу та посилення значущості роздрібно-го торгівлі для економіки країни; зміни в структурі реалізації продовольчих та непродовольчих товарів у бік нарощування продажів продовольства; підвищення рівня роздрібно-го товарообігу на одну особу в містах та селах України; розширення різновидів каналів збуту продукції; зростання торгових площ в Україні; укрупнення бізнесу та зменшення кількості малих торгових об'єктів; географічні відмінності в динаміці торговельних площ.

Ключові слова: торговельне підприємство, роздрібно-го торгівля, товарообіг, роздрібно-го торговельна мережа, зовнішнє середовище.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ТОРГОВЛИ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ

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Проанализированы современные тенденции развития предприятий торговли в Украине. Представлены результаты ключевых показателей деятельности предприятий розничной торговли в динамике и исследованы направления развития локальных торговых сетей.

Ключевые слова: торговое предприятие, розничная торговля, товарооборот, розничная торговая сеть, внешняя среда.

Statement of the problem. In present-day Ukraine, there are negative trends in the economy caused by the destabilization of the regions, which leads to an imbalance in the development of industries, including trade. It is in such conditions of constant imbalance of market situation the management of trade enterprises requires sufficient information about the state of both internal factors and the external environment (demand for goods, price policy of competitors, general economic and social trends). Significance of solving the problems of finding reserves of economy, profit growth and profitability, provided that the risks are eliminated or reduced, determines the need to improve the organization and methods of integrated economic analysis and internal control that can ensure an appropriate level of competitiveness of commercial enterprises.

The process of reforming the economy of Ukraine is accompanied with the socio-economic changes relating to a wide range of activities and industries, in particular the sphere of retail trade, which is determined by the competitive behavior of individual enterprises. The result of economic reform of trade in the modern competitive environment is a multiplicity of forms of ownership and the possibility of developing different types of commercial enterprises. Trade holds a significant share of gross domestic product. In fact, if in 1990 trade and restaurant economy provided 4.5% of Ukraine's GDP, then in 1995 this share increased to 5.9%, in 2005 – 11.0%, and after the 2010 it reached 14.0%, and in 2016 – 17.2%, which is an important factor of economic growth.

Review of the latest research and publications. The main objective of the trading enterprise is to achieve advantages in a competitive environment, ensuring high rates of development in a strategic perspective and the growth of value. Considerable attention is paid to this problem by such scientists as A.A. Mazaraki, L.O. Ligonenko [1;2]. They focus on retail, which aims to meet the needs of consumers and ensure social reproduction. The key element that determines the conditions for achieving the competitiveness of the enterprise is the competitive environment.

One of the main indicators of economic activity of trade enterprises and an important factor in ensuring sustainable economic growth of the country as a whole is commodity circulation. Its volume, structure and dynamics are not only one of the main characteristics of the state of domestic trade and an indicator of the need for changes, but also allow to assess the effectiveness of the planned activities for the implementation of the strategic trade development program. The existing problems of trade development in Ukraine should be solved in the direction of accelerated increase in commodity circulation between the residents of the national economy.

The objective of the research is to clarify the current trends in the development of trade enterprises and an analytical assessment of their performance in dynamics.

Presentation of the research material. Trade plays a significant role in the formation of a competitive environment, the implementation of social policy and market orientation of the national economy, because it is a channel of promotion of products to the consumer, a type of economic activity, the object of which is the exchange and service of buyers for the sale of goods, their transportation, storage and preparation for sale.

The activity of trade enterprises in a competitive environment leads to the need of expanding the scope of their economic activity. Trade is decisive in balancing production and consumption, thereby forming a significant share of gross value added, providing employment, because today in this area employs a sixth of the total economically active population, which corresponds to the level of economically developed countries.

Commodity circulation is one of the most important macroeconomic indicators of social and economic development of the country as a whole and each of its regions in particular. State statistical bodies at different levels of government collect and process data on commodity circulation in order to identify common patterns and trends, the place of individual sub-markets, analyze interregional exchange, social and regional differences in the levels of commodity circulation per capita. The latter characterizes the processes taking place in the sphere of commodity turnover, and is an indicator that changes the cost of consumer goods formed in the production process. It also affects the state of money turnover in the country, the stability of the national currency, determines the scale of foreign economic activity, budget revenues and other macroeconomic indicators.

The volume of attracting cash income of consumers, the size and structure of social needs, the scale and degree of satisfaction of demand for goods, living standards, material and cultural well-being of the population of the country allow us to estimate the volume and structure of retail commodity circulation, which, by definition of N.V. Stasyuk, is a complex system of social and economic relations of social reproduction at the stage of exchange of cash income of the population for consumer goods [3]. This interpretation emphasizes the fulfillment of the most important social function by the commodity circulation – improving the welfare and quality of life of the population, and in the end – the health of the nation.

Regulation of retail commodity circulation at the macro level requires consideration of the entire set of subjects of commercial entrepreneurship to assess the overall macroeconomic value of commodity circulation indicators in the context of the characteristics of the sphere of

commodity turnover. Given this, the study of tendentious, structural, regional features of the development of retail trade is a necessary prerequisite for determining the priorities of the regulatory impact of the state on the production and infrastructure of the market, meet social needs and improve the living standards of the population. As is known, the effectiveness of economic analysis depends on the quality of information support, which has the following basic requirements: utility, relevance, reliability, credibility, clarity, comparability and stability.

Analysis of indicators of retail trade development in Ukraine was carried out on the basis of official data of the state statistics service of Ukraine [4].

A result of research of dynamics of development of retail commodity circulation for the analyzed period from 1996 to 2016 (Fig. 1) establishes the following:

- there is a steady trend of growth in the total and actual volume of retail commodity circulation against the background of different intensity;
- the most intensive growth process took place in the period from 2004 to 2008, the chain rate of change for this period is 137.3 %; however, the highest growth rate of retail commodity circulation is seen in 1996 (145%), but due to the price factor, mainly the increase in its physical volume is 103.8%;
- a noticeable decline in the dynamics of retail commodity circulation is observed in the peak periods of the crisis, namely, a reduction in the rate in 2009 compared to 2008 to 94.2%, in contrast to the previous growth in 2008 compared to 2007 by 136%, which is an adequate reflection of the global financial crisis;
- the following disastrous period in 2012 becomes the year in which the increase in the rate of retail commodity circulation amounted to 109% with further decrease of this indicator to 101% in 2014.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of retail commodity circulation in 1996–2016

Thus, the dynamics of the retail trade indicator most clearly demonstrates the sensitivity of consumer demand to the development of crisis phenomena. It should be noted that a significant contribution to the growth of the actual retail turnover in recent years of the analyzed period was created by an extensive factor, namely the rapid growth of prices for consumer goods. Generally, over the past twenty years, retail trade turnover through the retail network in Ukraine has increased almost 32.1 times (from 17344.0 million UAH in 1996 to 555975.0 mln UAH in 2016), but this is not enough to argue about the qualitative growth in the retail sector, as it is necessary to take into account the inflationary processes that have occurred and are taking place in the country.

Despite the rapid increase in the volume of retail commodity circulation for the entire study period, the total number of retail facilities engaged in retail trade of consumer goods in Ukraine is decreasing (in 1996 it was 132.0 thousand units, and in 2008 – only 69.2 thousand units, and in 2016, this figure is 49.3 thousand units only.). At the same time, the decrease in the number of retail facilities occurred in all sectors of trade (by ownership) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Dynamics of number of retail trade enterprises in 1996–2016

The reduction in the number of outlets occurs with the simultaneous growth of their area. This phenomenon is evidenced by the process of globalization in the internal trade of Ukraine. On the one hand, the number of retail facilities with significant retail space (supermarkets, hypermarkets,

etc.) grows, and on the other hand, there is a reduction in the number of small shops that do not have enough competitive advantages to compete with big business. The average area of one store increases simultaneously in cities and villages, but the priority location of small retail facilities remains rural.

A noticeable trend in 2017 was the active development of local retail chains covering one economic and geographical region. According to Igor Guglia, Director of consulting company GT Partners Ukraine, last year in the segment of mini-markets the most actively growing networks were Tochka (47 stores) in Odessa, Faino Market (63 stores) in Kropyvnytskyi, and Kyiv network Lotok. For example, the Faino Market, according to the company, opened 18 new stores in 2017. A network Lotok, which has 87 outlets, only for last year opened 22 new stores near the house. The activity of local players is due to the concentration in the regions that are familiar and understandable to them, as well as their development mainly in the popular format "shop near the house".

For such shops, it is easier to find suitable premises. In addition, we can note that the basis of the format of the store at home is already "laid" a high degree of customer loyalty due to the location. Another possible reason for the activity of regional players lies in the statistics of market leaders, who slightly slowed down the pace of development.

In particular, the group of companies Fozzy Group last year focused on the development of fora network within the capital region. The company also began to pay more attention to its discounter Thrash, opening these stores on the site of the least profitable Silpo and thus giving a second chance to the trading location. The leader of the domestic retail market, ATB Corporation, has somewhat reduced the pace of development. If in 2016 the company opened 111 stores, in 2017 – 78. We also recall that the company is currently aimed at conquering the western region of the country and expanding the logistics infrastructure of the network. Thus, at the end of 2016, it acquired several stores Barvinok, and last year bought part of the assets of the Kolibris network. This year, ATB Corporation plans to open more than 100 new stores, mainly in the western region, Odessa region and Kyiv.

The priority of placing retailers in cities is explained by a number of factors: firstly, a significant concentration of the population; secondly, the presence of solvent buyers; thirdly, the trend of increasing the construction of residential buildings in cities requires the creation of additional social infrastructure-shops, kiosks, markets and the like. A significant contribution to the development of retail trade in cities creates a reduction in the amount of free time of the working population.

For such people, various types of shops are becoming relevant, located mainly near their place of residence, with an extended work schedule, or in general, shops of round-the-clock trade.

One of the problems of retail trade is related to the expansion of foreign trade capital and imports, as well as the internationalization of domestic trade. With the liberalization of trade, the integration of the national economy into international relations, the flow of imported goods in the Ukrainian market increases, which leads to significant imbalances in the structure of commodity circulation. The share of goods produced in Ukraine in commodity circulation decreased from 58% to 35% and continues to decline. About 10 leading commodity groups in the commodity circulation is formed exclusively of imports. There is another problem related to imports – the expansion of foreign trade capital.

Foreign direct investments in domestic trade is characterized by stable positive dynamics. In 2000–2016, they increased by 7.5 times and therefore trade came to second place among all economic activities, second only to the manufacturing industry. Along the way, we emphasize that domestic investments in fixed assets are also characterized by high rates, while foreign and domestic investments have different directions.

While domestic investors invest primarily in retail trade, foreign investors direct capital to the most backward and most important wholesale sector in the future. The activity of investments leads to the emergence of a new phenomenon in domestic trade – the internationalization of its objects, that is, the creation of objects (distributors, wholesale operators, supermarkets, hypermarkets) with the participation of foreign capital. Finally, the result of internationalization is as follows: domestic traders are forced out of traditional markets. Over 2000–2016, not less than 10 thousand stores have closed. Accordingly, internationalization is not a purely adapted process. It produces positive results only in equal economic systems, while in other cases negative social and economic consequences are inevitable.

For many years, inflation is the «engine» of Ukrainian trade, says RAU with reference to the publication Business. According to preliminary estimates of GT Partners Ukraine, sales of Ukrainian grocery chains in 2017 increased by at least 15% and exceeded 250 billion UAH. According to a GfK's study, last year the cost of the consumer basket (includes more than 80 product categories: food, beverages, detergents, household chemicals, personal hygiene items) increased by 19% compared to 2016. At the same time, this growth is due to the rise in price of the goods. While the real (quantitative) consumption has not changed – it has increased only by 0.1%.

Taking into account the fact that some companies leave the market and others come, the total number of players in the grocery retail in recent

years has not changed significantly. Last year in the country there were such networks as Kupava market (four stores) in Ternopil and Schedryi market (four stores) in Lutsk. In addition, the investment group VolWestGroup (network Nash Krai) began to develop the SPAR network in Ukraine. In 2017, it was planned to open 15 stores, and in the next three years – 50 outlets. Newcomers to the market appear this year. In particular, the media reported that the restaurant company L'Kafa Group opens in Kyiv its first store in the house Bazaar Express in March. Restaurateurs plan in two or three years to create a network of 30–40 outlets.

Given the development plans of major players, as well as trends in trade, large networks will gradually overtake small ones and increase their market share. While individual local networks are developing, because they have not found their niche, they generate losses, the trading network pays off in the presence of 50 stores and more. Therefore, in our opinion, few local players will compete with large retailers, and regional networks will eventually leave the market. In our opinion, despite the current fragmentation of the market, its consolidation is inevitable. Ukrainian market of grocery retailing is still difficult to name highly consolidated. Major players are mainly fighting for the location, not for business. This is due to the fact that potential challengers for "takeover" do not have a clear positioning, as well as a shortage of suitable retail space. But market consolidation is a growing global trend that allows players to increase their share, strengthen their position in the market and offer an interesting price through economies of scale. And Ukraine is no exception.

An example of consolidation of players was the acquisition last summer by Auchan of nine hypermarkets Caravan. Due to this operation, the international retailer has increased the number of outlets in Ukraine to 20, their total area was 160 600 sq. m. This allowed the company to enter new cities for the network – Kharkiv, Dnipro, Kherson, Chernivtsi. It should be noted that not all international players presented in the Ukrainian market are developing dynamically. Apparently, the Ukrainian market in the company Novus is considered to be promising, because it is not the only operator that has been building large stores in the country "from scratch" in recent years.

Different research companies structure retail sales channels and store formats in their own way. However, analysts agree that in recent years stores of small areas and easy accessibility actively develop. According to a GfK's study, if in 2016, according to the growth rates in Ukraine, the leading discounters and Cash & Carry, then last year – specialized stores, supermarkets and shops near the house. Specialized stores increased turnover by increasing the share of more expensive products in the range, which allowed to attract new customers, and hypermarkets, on the contrary,

offering more expensive products, lost part of their customers, but the remaining visitors began to buy in hypermarkets more often. Also, according to the consumer panel of households of GfK, last year the number of online purchases doubled, although their share in the total structure of sales of goods of daily demand remains insignificant – 0.1%. Note that the average cost of buying on the Internet has decreased, and the frequency and size of purchases have increased, indicating that buyers have become more likely to buy online not only perfumes and expensive cosmetics, as it was in previous years, but also food.

Perhaps, given the growing popularity of home shops in the country, some retailers who have not developed this format before are going to master it. In particular, the company Auchan presented in the segment of hypermarkets, at the beginning of last year announced plans to open in Ukraine their points in the format of shops at home. According to the company GT Partners Ukraine, in recent years in Ukraine opens more minimarkets (self-service stores up to 200 square meters). In our opinion, this is facilitated by a large offer of vacant premises for stores of this format. While finding a room for a supermarket is much more difficult. In addition, these stores have a short payback period (one and a half to three years) and return on investment. And smaller investments – \$20000–30000 per 100 sq. m. This year's forecast experts do not expect revolutionary changes in the Ukrainian food retail market. The situation will not change dramatically. Local operators will continue to develop within their regions. National ones will develop organically by opening stores or looking for an opportunity to overtake small ones. "Foreign players are not interested in the Ukrainian food retail market. They look at the purchasing power of the population. And the payback period of 7–12 years does not inspire anyone".

According to the company GT Partners Ukraine, there are about 150 companies in Ukraine, which include retail chains, if you count the number of stores from two. The country has seven national operators, ATB, Fozzy Group, VolWestGroup, ECO Market, Furshet, Tavria-B and Retail Group (Velyka Kyshenya, Velmart, VK Express), if consider the national companies that are present in four of the five economic and geographic regions of Ukraine. Local retailers, according to GT Partners Ukraine, comprise 83% of the total number of players. And, as already mentioned, two or three new operators enter the market every year.

Conclusion. Thus, it can be concluded that in the near future the efforts of national retailers will be aimed at optimizing primarily existing retail chains, increasing their efficiency and profitability, and efforts will be aimed at reducing the cost of borrowed resources.

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КЛАСИФІКАЦІЯ КОНКУРЕНТНИХ ПЕРЕВАГ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ РОЗДРІБНОЇ ТОРГІВЛІ

А.М. Волосов

Досліджено наукові підходи до класифікації конкурентних переваг. Виділено два напрями можливої класифікації: перший – залежно від змістового наповнення типології конкурентних переваг; другий – з урахуванням специфічних особливостей роздрібної торгівлі. Перший напрям доповнено такими ознаками: активні стадії життєвого циклу, ступінь ризику, темп змін. За другим напрямом виділено ознаки класифікації конкурентних переваг підприємств ритейлу, що відображають специфіку роздрібної торгівлі.

***Ключові слова:** конкурентні переваги, класифікація, роздрібна торгівля, життєвий цикл, ризик, темп змін.*

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ КОНКУРЕНТНЫХ ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ РОЗНИЧНОЙ ТОРГОВЛИ

А.М. Волосов

Рассмотрены научные подходы к классификации конкурентных преимуществ. Выделены два направления возможной классификации: